

Main Theme	Details
Not a privacy concern	Not privacy problem
Reasonable camera usage	Outdoor camera is acceptable Host has the right to outdoor camera
Ask for controllability	Ask for more controllability
Transparency	Need more information about details of usage Privacy infringement
Comments on Privacy Negotiation	Communicate with respect and cooperative attitude Negotiating through text is a good means of communication Contact Airbnb Alternative accommodations
Monetary Compensation	Ask for a full refund Monetary compensation does not address privacy concerns

Table 1: Summary of reasons why participants negotiate in Driveway Camera Context

Main Theme	Details
Physical adjustment of devices	Cover the device Remove the device Disable the device Unplug the device
Why Negotiation	Express privacy concerns Value privacy Uncomfortable with in-door camera
Negotiation Methods	Contact Airbnb Continue privacy negotiation
Not a privacy concern	Trust the host Both reach to an agreement Partial refund is a good deal
Monetary Compensation	Ask for a full refund Monetary compensation does not solve privacy problems

Table 2: Summary of reasons why participants negotiate in Smart TV Context

Main Theme	Details
Physical adjustment of devices	Cover the device Remove the device Disable the device Unplug the device
Why Negotiation	Express privacy concerns Value privacy
Negotiation Methods	Contact Airbnb Continue privacy negotiation Communicate with respect and cooperative attitude Face-to-face negotiation Clear Airbnb guideline
Not a privacy concern	Easy Approach Both reach to an agreement Partial refund is a good deal
Monetary Compensation	Ask for a full refund Monetary compensation does not solve privacy problems

Table 3: Summary of reasons why participants negotiate in Voice Assistant Context

Main Theme	Details
Physical adjustment of devices	Remove the camera Adjust the camera position Disable the camera during stay Turn off the camera Cover the camera
Negotiation Methods	Call host Face-to-face negotiation Contact Airbnb Smooth the negotiation
Concerns and Policies	Express concern Clear Airbnb guideline Refer to Airbnb policy Full refund requested Monetary compensation does not solve privacy problems
Transparency	All things should be disclosed before booking Check for all other potential devices Clarification on usage (e.g., when, how)
Perspectives and Views	Host Perspective: Has right to protect their property Guest Perspective: Will be safer during stay Outdoor camera is acceptable
Responses and Outcomes	No change Both have reached a satisfactory agreement Written assurance Reply fast Automated reply Automated reply and prompts

Table 4: Summary of modification of participants on Smart Home Privacy Negotiation in Driveway Camera Context

Main Theme	Details
Ask for controllability	Remove the device Disable the device Turn off the device Cover the device Unplug the device
Future Design for Negotiation	Face to face negotiation preferred Continue to negotiation rather than accept a refund
Negotiation Methods	Elaborate privacy concerns Check for all other potential devices Disclose beforehand Check Airbnb's policies Oversight from Airbnb

Table 5: Summary of modification of participants on Smart Home Privacy Negotiation in Smart TV Context

Main Theme	Details
Ask for controllability	Ask for controllability during stay Cover the camera Remove the device Disable the camera Unplug the TV or camera
Negotiation Methods	Express privacy concerns Value privacy Contact Airbnb Continue privacy negotiation Uncomfortable with in-door camera
Responses and Outcomes	Trust the host Both reach to an agreement Partial refund is a good deal
Monetary Compensation	Ask for a full refund Monetary compensation does not solve privacy problems

Table 6: Summary of modification of participants on Smart Home Privacy Negotiation in Voice Assistant Context

Main Theme	Details
Satisfaction with Privacy Negotiation Outcomes	Both Have Reached a Satisfactory Agreement Host Provides Fair Deal Guest Perspective: Will Be Safer During Stay Host Perspective: Has Right to Protect Their Property
Actions Taken by Guests to Protect Privacy	Remove or Adjust Device Location Cover the Camera Ask for Controllability Report to Third Party Contact Airbnb Continue to Negotiate Leave a Review About the Experience Change to Another Rental Find Alternative Accommodation
Transparency	All Information Should Be Disclosed Before Booking
Monetary Compensation	Monetary Compensation Does Not Solve Privacy Problems Full Refund Requested Money Loss Experienced
Acceptable Privacy Protection Measures	Comfortable with Outdoor Camera Outdoor Camera Is Acceptable

Table 7: Summary of satisfactions of participants on Smart Home Privacy Negotiation in Driveway Context

Main Theme	Details
Device Control	Cover the camera or device Unplug or disconnect the device Disable the device or camera Relocation or remove the device/camera
Transparency	All things should be disclosed before booking Seek information beforehand about the property Check for all other potential devices
Privacy Concerns and Suspicion	Suspicious of audio recording or other surveillance Concern about privacy violations Suspicious of hosts' motives
Negotiation Recommendations	Communicate further with the host Report to Airbnb Report to other authorities Cite Airbnb policy in communications or reviews Ask for travel companies' suggestion Seek paper guarantee Check Airbnb privacy policy Seek more empathy from the host
Refunds and Monetary Concerns	Monetary compensation does not solve privacy problems Jane loses money
Review and Feedback	Leave a review about the experience
Alternative Solutions	Refund in exchange for privacy
Usage Restrictions and Precautions	Not use TV or limit its use Ask about other devices to understand surveillance scope

Table 8: Summary of satisfactions of participants on Smart Home Privacy Negotiation in Smart TV Context

Main Theme	Details
Device Control	Cover the camera or device Unplug or disconnect the device Disable the device or camera Relocation or remove the device/camera
Transparency	All things should be disclosed before booking Seek information beforehand about the property Check for all other potential devices
Privacy Concerns and Suspicion	Suspicious of audio recording or other surveillance Concern about privacy violations Suspicious of hosts' motives
Negotiation Recommendations	Communicate further with the host Report to Airbnb Report to other authorities Cite Airbnb policy in communications or reviews Ask for travel companies' suggestion Seek paper guarantee Check Airbnb privacy policy
Refunds and Monetary Concerns	Monetary compensation does not solve privacy problems Don't want to lose money
Review and Feedback	Leave a review about the experience Post on social media Threatening bad reviews
Outcome Satisfaction	Satisfied with accommodation Satisfied with privacy negotiation outcome Both have reached a satisfactory agreement Accept partial refund Accept the refund Based on discount SHD is host's property Comfortable with outdoor camera Airbnb policy should ban such devices Leave the rental to protect privacy Jane is overreacting/used to camera in the rental

Table 9: Summary of satisfactions of participants on Smart Home Privacy Negotiation in Voice Assistant Context